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A Pattern To Evil: The Anatomy of Three Genocides

by

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Abstract: The paper discusses the quest to identify patterns in notorious mass atrocities of the 20th century in Europe, specifically focusing on three genocides: Jasenovac, Volhynia, and Srebrenica. The goal is to analyze the socio-economic and political circumstances surrounding these events and address the complexities of understanding historical realities. The work aims to review historical circumstances, media coverage, memorials, reconciliation efforts, and official apologies related to these genocides. It also explores the possibility of an empirical approach to understanding these events.

The distinct nature of the three genocides is reflected, highlighting the extreme violence and targeted killings of specific ethnic or religious groups. The text delves into the complexities of defining genocide and distinguishing it from ethnic cleansing, emphasizing the intentional and systematic nature of the destruction of specific groups. The paper also provides insights into the systematic and deliberate nature of ethnic cleansing, which involves the removal or elimination of specific ethnic or religious groups from a particular area.

Overall, the text aims to unravel the complexities and nuances of these historical atrocities and seeks to understand the emergence of genocide and ethnic cleansing through a multidimensional lens.

A Pattern To Evil: The Anatomy of Three Genocides

“All is not lost, the unconquerable will, and study of revenge,
immortal hate, and the courage never to submit or yield.”

John Milton¹

Is there an equation of evil? Will seeking a pattern in notorious mass atrocities in the XX century in Europe give any answers to this question?

The goal of this work is to dissect three genocides that occurred in Europe in the XX century and observe whether there is any pattern regarding the socio-economic and political circumstances before, during, and after the atrocities were committed, according to the records in relevant literature.

So, how does anyone approach such impervious subjects that still, after decades of their occurrences, spur dispute and argument?

This paper will try to review the following parameters: the historical circumstances prior to the occurrences of the genocides; the general or immediate history of the region and documented inceptions of violence hitherto; media coverage; as well as memorials and remembrance. Also, an attempt will be made to obtain answers to the question: have the opposing sides been reconciled, and has anyone apologized in the form of an official apology?

History is rarely strictly black and white. That is why information from diverse sources and acknowledging the limitations of available evidence are essential for understanding complex historical realities. Yet, a documented crime and an atrocity is in the realm of scientifically and legally acknowledged facts.

Is there any possibility for an empirical approach? Let's give it a try.

¹ From *Paradise Lost* (1667), book 1

Three notorious war crimes

The genocides in Jasenovac, Volhynia, and Srebrenica, respectively, are all tragic events in European history that involved mass killings of civilians during different periods of time, in different contexts, and in divergent geographical positions. Jasenovac was a concentration camp and extermination camp operated by the Ustasha regime in the Independent State of Croatia (NDH), during the second World War. It was primarily targeted against Serbs, Jews, and Roma people², and it is estimated that between 77,000 and 100,000 people were killed there.³ There are some estimations that the numbers were as high as 750,000⁴. The Volhynia massacre was a series of ethnic cleansing actions carried out by the Ukrainian Insurgent Army (UPA) against Polish civilians in the Volhynia region of Ukraine from 1943 to 1945. The UPA targeted Polish men, women, and children, resulting in the deaths of tens of thousands of Poles.⁵ The Srebrenica massacre was the mass murder of Bosniak men and boys by Bosnian Serb forces in the town of Srebrenica during the Bosnian War in 1995⁶. It is estimated that over 8,000 Bosniak men and boys were killed, and it represents a textbook study for the concept of gendercide⁷.

While all three genocides were characterized by extreme violence and targeted killings of specific ethnic or religious groups, they occurred in different historical contexts and were carried out by different perpetrators. However, they all resulted in the tragic loss of innocent lives and have had long-lasting impacts on the affected communities.

Can evil be defined?

How could we even try to begin grasping the emergence of genocide? Genocide is a complex and legally defined term referring to the intentional destruction, in whole or in part, of a national, ethnic,

² Prusin, A. V. (2017). *Serbia under the Swastika*. University of Illinois. p.37

³ Miletić, A (1986). *Koncentracioni Logor Jasenovac - Knjiga I*. Narodna knjiga.

⁴ Neubacher, F. (2006). How Can it Happen that Horrendous State Crimes are Perpetrated?: An Overview of Criminological Theories. *Journal of International Criminal Justice*, 4(4), 787–799.

⁵ Himka, J.P. (2021). *Ukrainian Nationalists and the Holocaust - OUN and UPA's Participation in the Destruction of Ukrainian Jewry, 1941–1944*. Ukrainian Voices - ibidem Press.

⁶ Honig, J.W., Both, N. (1997). Srebrenica, hronika ratnog zločina. Ljiljan.

⁷ Jones, A. (2000). Gendercide and genocide. *Journal of Genocide Research*, 2:2, 185-211.

racial, or religious group. This destruction goes beyond the Crime of Genocide, adopted by the United Nations in 1948, which includes: intent, targeted groups, and acts that include killing members of the group in the form of massacres, executions, or causing serious bodily or mental harm, imposing living conditions intended to destroy the group, such as starvation, disease, or preventing births within the group with forced sterilization or abortions, as well as forcibly transferring children of the group to another group, thus breaking family bonds and cultural identity. The elements that distinguish genocide from other forms of violence are its specificity - the targeting of a specific group based on their identity, not random individuals: and its scale and Intent - the aim is to permanently eliminate the group, not just suppress or displace them.

One of the pioneers in defining genocide, Raphael Lemkin, a Polish-Jewish lawyer and the coiner of the term "genocide" itself, who played a key role in the drafting and adoption of the United Nations Genocide Convention in 1948, defined it as "a coordinated plan of different actions aiming at the destruction of the essential foundations of the life of national groups, with the aim of annihilating the groups themselves."⁸ Barbara Harff, an American political scientist known for her work on genocide and political violence, has argued that: "genocide is a form of one-sided mass killing in which a state or other authority intends to destroy a group, as that group and membership in it are defined by the perpetrator."⁹ The United Nations Genocide Convention mentioned above defines genocide as "the deliberate destruction, in whole or in part, by a government or its agents, of a racial, sexual, religious, tribal, or political minority." These definitions provide different perspectives on the concept of genocide, highlighting the intentional and systematic nature of the destruction of specific groups¹⁰.

Having this in mind, could we make a distinction between genocide and ethnic cleansing?

Ethnic cleansing refers to the systematic forced removal of an ethnic, racial, or religious group from a certain area with the intent of making the region ethnically homogeneous. This "removal" can be achieved through various methods, including: direct violence (massacres, executions, forced displacement, and intimidation), indirect coercion (destruction of property, cultural sites, and

⁸ Lemkin, R. (1944). *Axis Rule in occupied Europe. Laws of occupation. Analysis of government. Proposals for redress.* Carnegie Endowment for international peace, Division of international law.

⁹ Barbara Harff, B., Gurr, T. B. (2018). *Preventing Mass Atrocities-Policies and Practices.* Routledge.

¹⁰ The Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, on 9 December 1948.

livelihoods, creating unbearable conditions for the targeted group), deportation (forcible expulsion of the group from the territory), and assimilation (forcing the targeted group to abandon their cultural identity and assimilate into the dominant group). While not all instances of violence against a specific group constitute ethnic cleansing, key characteristics differentiate it from other forms of persecution. These include systematicity - planned and organized actions against the targeted group, not isolated incidents; intent - the ultimate goal is to permanently change the region's demographic makeup; and widespread - targeting the entire group or a significant portion of it, not just individuals or dissidents. Bell-Fialkoff delves into the origins and evolution of ethnic cleansing as a "strategy of exclusion and displacement¹¹."

The United Nations Commission of Experts, established by the UN Security Council to investigate and report on violations of international humanitarian law in the former Yugoslavia, has formulated ethnic cleansing as "the planned deliberate removal from a specific territory of persons of a particular ethnic group, by force or intimidation, in order to render that area ethnically homogenous." Ethnic Studies scholar and author Renée Hirschon, known for her work on ethnic identity and conflict in southeastern Europe, argues that "ethnic cleansing is the mass expulsion or killing of members of one ethnic or religious group in an area by those of another."¹² The political scientist and genocide scholar Norman Naimark, who has written extensively on ethnic cleansing and genocide in Eastern Europe, writes: "Ethnic cleansing is a purposeful policy designed by one ethnic or religious group to remove by violent and terror-inspiring means the civilian population of another ethnic or religious group from certain geographic areas¹³." These definitions provide insight into the systematic and deliberate nature of ethnic cleansing, which involves the removal or elimination of specific ethnic or religious groups from a particular area.

Jasenovac

Jasenovac was a complex of concentration and extermination camps established and operated by the Ustasha regime in the Independent State of Croatia between 1941 and 1945. It was one of the largest and most notorious concentration camps in Europe, known for its brutal treatment of prisoners,

¹¹Bell-Fialkoff, A. (1992). A Brief History of Ethnic Cleansing. *Foreign Affairs*, 3,(72), 110-121.

¹² (Forced Migration_ 12) Renée Hirschon (editor) - *Crossing the Aegean_ An Appraisal of the 1923 Compulsory Population Exchange between Greece and Turkey*-Berghahn Books (2003)

¹³ Naimark, Norman M. *Fires of hatred : ethnic cleansing in twentieth-century Europe*, First Harvard University Press paperback edition, 2002

making it a symbol of brutal violence and systematic genocide¹⁴, claiming the lives of an estimated 77,000 to 100,000 people. The majority of victims were Serbs, targeted due to the Ustaša ideology of creating an ethnically homogeneous Croatia. However, Jews, Roma, and political opponents also suffered persecution and murder. Jasenovac was a complex with five sub-camps serving different functions. Some held prisoners for forced labor, while others primarily focused on extermination. Killing methods included mass shootings, gassing, hangings, bludgeoning, starvation, and exposure to harsh elements. The Ustaša were known for their extreme cruelty, inflicting torture and suffering on their victims. While not widely known, Jasenovac was one of the deadliest concentration camps in Europe during World War II.

Historical circumstances prior to the Jasenovac concentration camp

The Balkans, where Jasenovac is situated, are known for their diverse ethnic, religious, and cultural groups and their history of political and social upheaval. Following World War I, the multi-ethnic Kingdom of Yugoslavia was formed, uniting Serbs, Croats, Slovenes, Macedonians, and Montenegrins. However, ethnic and political tensions simmered beneath the surface. The assassination of King Alexander I in 1934 by a Croatian nationalist further strained relations. By the late 1930s, nationalist movements advocating for separate nation-states gained momentum, particularly among Croats. The Ustaša, a fascist and Croatian nationalist movement led by Ante Pavelić, sought an independent Croatia based on an exclusivist vision of Croatian identity. In 1941, the Axis powers invaded and occupied Yugoslavia, leading to the establishment of the Independent State of Croatia, which was controlled by the Ustasha regime when brutal measures were implemented against ethnic and religious minorities.

Documented inceptions of violence in the region before World War II?

The region where Jasenovac is located has a history of violence and conflict prior to World War II. The Balkans, including the area that was part of the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, experienced a series of conflicts and tensions, often rooted in ethnic, religious, and political differences. One notable example is the Balkan Wars of 1912-1913, which were a series of conflicts between the Balkan states and the

¹⁴ Goldstein, Ivo; Goldstein, Slavko (2016). The Holocaust in Croatia. University of Pittsburgh

Ottoman Empire. These wars resulted in significant territorial changes and the redrawing of borders in the region. The aftermath of these wars contributed to ethnic and political tensions, particularly as different ethnic groups found themselves living within newly defined borders. Additionally, during the interwar period, the Kingdom of Yugoslavia faced internal challenges related to ethnic and religious diversity. Tensions between different ethnic groups, such as Serbs, Croats, and others, sometimes led to violent confrontations and political unrest. One particularly notable event was the assassination of Archduke Franz Ferdinand of Austria in Sarajevo in 1914, which sparked World War I. This assassination took place in the region and had far-reaching consequences for the entire continent.

Jasenovac concentration camp in the media

During World War II, the media coverage of the Jasenovac concentration camp was limited and often influenced by the propaganda efforts of the warring parties. The information about the atrocities committed in Jasenovac was not widely disseminated at the time, and the full extent of the horrors that took place there was not immediately known to the international community and was unreliable. Early reports emerged through escapees and resistance movements, painting a horrifying picture but lacking concrete details. The Ustasha regime in the Independent State of Croatia tightly controlled the flow of information and used propaganda to present a sanitized and distorted image of the camp. They sought to conceal the true nature of the atrocities and downplay the scale of the crimes committed at Jasenovac.

However, despite these efforts, some reports and testimonies about the brutal conditions and mass killings at Jasenovac did manage to reach the outside world. These reports were often circulated by underground resistance movements, individuals who managed to escape from the camp, or through clandestine channels.

In the post-war period, during the Socialist federation of Yugoslavia, a narrative of "brotherhood and unity" downplayed the Ustaša's crimes and minimized discussions of ethnic tensions, but despite official silence, survivors' testimonies and memoirs kept the memory of Jasenovac alive. However, public discourse remained limited by political constraints. With the dissolution of Yugoslavia, historical reassessments emerged, bringing wider attention to Jasenovac. International institutions recognized it as a concentration camp, leading to increased research and documentation. Media coverage intensified, highlighting the camp's brutality and the suffering of victims. Documentaries, articles, and exhibitions brought wider awareness to the public. Despite increased attention, controversies and debates persist.

Issues like victim numbers, historical interpretations, and ongoing nationalist tensions continue to challenge a comprehensive and sensitive understanding of Jasenovac.

Today, Jasenovac is recognized as one of the most notorious concentration camps of the Holocaust, and efforts to preserve its memory and ensure that the truth about its history is known continue. This includes historical research, educational initiatives, and commemorative events aimed at honoring the victims and raising awareness about the camp's significance.

Memorial and remembrance

The site of the former camp has been transformed into a memorial and museum dedicated to honoring the victims and educating visitors about the history and significance of Jasenovac. The Jasenovac Memorial Site, located in modern-day Croatia, is recognized by UNESCO as part of the "Memory of the World" register. The area has a museum which houses permanent and occasional exhibitions documenting the camp's history, featuring artifacts, survivor testimonies, and historical documents; a memorial park that includes various monuments and memorials honoring the victims, with sculptures, symbolic gardens, and inscribed names of identified victims; a research center that conducts research on the camp's history, collects testimonies, and provides educational resources; as well as an archive that houses Regular events are organized, including commemorations, educational programs, seminars, and conferences, to ensure the tragedy is not forgotten.

Have the opposing sides been reconciled, and has anyone apologized?

The reconciliation between the opposing sides related to the Jasenovac concentration camp remains a complex, incomplete, and sensitive issue. The history of the camp and the atrocities committed there are deeply intertwined with the complex ethnic, religious, and political dynamics of the region, which have led to ongoing tensions and divisions.

In the post-war period, the legacy of Jasenovac has been a subject of contention and debate, particularly among different ethnic and national communities in the region. Acknowledging and addressing the atrocities committed at Jasenovac has been a complex and often contentious issue, and historical narratives about the camp have sometimes been politicized.

Efforts at reconciliation and apology related to Jasenovac have been limited and have not fully addressed the grievances and suffering of all affected communities. While there have been some

statements of remorse and acknowledgment of the crimes committed at Jasenovac by certain political and religious leaders, comprehensive and universally accepted apologies have not been forthcoming. For example, Croatia's then-President Stipe Mesić expressed his "deepest regret" in 2003, but this statement didn't explicitly acknowledge genocide or fully satisfy victim groups¹⁵. On the other hand, certain groups, particularly nationalists in Croatia and Bosnia, continue to deny or downplay the atrocities committed at Jasenovac. This hinders genuine reconciliation and healing.

Croatia has made official statements acknowledging the suffering and atrocities that occurred at the Jasenovac concentration camp. These statements have expressed remorse for the crimes committed during the Holocaust and World War II, including the suffering of the victims at Jasenovac. In 1998, the Croatian Parliament declared April 22nd a national day of remembrance for the victims of the Jasenovac concentration camp. In 2016, Croatia adopted a declaration condemning the crimes committed at Jasenovac and expressing condolences to the families of the victims. Eighty years after the beginning of the formation of the Jasenovac camp, Croatian President Zoran Milanović in 2021 called Jasenovac a "crime against humanity" and a "shameful page" in Croatian history, though his statement was criticized by some for not being a formal apology¹⁶.

Volhynia

The Volhynia Massacre was a series of ethnic and political conflicts that took place in the region of Volhynia, located in present-day Ukraine. The conflict primarily involved the Ukrainian Insurgent Army (UPA), a nationalist paramilitary organization, and the Polish population in the region. The massacre began in 1943 and continued into 1944, during which tens of thousands of Poles, including men, women, and children, were brutally killed¹⁷. Other groups: Jews, Belarusians, and Ukrainians—who collaborated with the Soviets were also targeted. The UPA, seeking to establish an independent Ukrainian state, targeted the Polish population in Volhynia as part of their efforts to remove perceived foreign influence from Ukrainian territories. The violence was characterized by brutal and indiscriminate attacks on Polish villages, resulting in widespread atrocities, including massacres, mutilations, and forced deportations. Starting in March 1943, the UPA launched coordinated attacks on Polish villages and settlements throughout Volhynia. These attacks were characterized by extreme brutality, with civilians being murdered using axes, knives, and other weapons.

¹⁵ Milekic, S. (2017). Croatia Ex-President Shown Downplaying WWII Crimes. *Balkan Transitional Justice*

¹⁶ Öztürk, M. T. (2021). Croatian president makes controversial statements on Srebrenica genocide. *Anadolu Agency*

¹⁷ Snyder, T. (2003). The Causes of the Volhynian Massacres in Poland. *Past & Present*, 179(1), 197–234.

The conflict also led to retaliatory actions by Polish self-defense units and the Polish Home Army, further escalating the violence and bloodshed. The Volhynia Massacre is a deeply tragic chapter in the history of Eastern Europe during World War II. The events have had a lasting impact on Polish-Ukrainian relations and continue to be the subject of historical research, remembrance, and efforts to promote reconciliation and understanding between the two nations. In recent years, there have been efforts by both Polish and Ukrainian authorities and civil society organizations to address the historical legacy of the Volhynia Massacre, foster dialogue, and promote mutual understanding and reconciliation. These efforts aim to acknowledge the suffering of the victims, promote historical truth, and work towards healing the wounds of the past.

Historical circumstances prior to the Volhynia massacre

Volhynia is a historical region in northwestern Ukraine, now part of the Rivne, Volyn, and Zhytomyr Oblasts. Several key historical factors contributed to the escalation of tensions and ultimately to the outbreak of violence in Volhynia: the interwar period - following the First World War and the collapse of the Russian, Austro-Hungarian, and German empires, saw the establishment of the Second Polish Republic and the Ukrainian People's Republic: Volhynia, a region with a mixed Polish and Ukrainian population, became a point of contention between these newly formed states; the borders of the Second Polish Republic and the Ukrainian People's Republic were contested, leading to disputes over territory and national identity: Volhynia, with its diverse population, became a focal point for these disputes, exacerbating ethnic tensions; the period was marked by conflicts between Polish authorities and Ukrainian nationalist movements seeking independence. In addition, the outbreak of World War II and the subsequent occupation of Eastern Europe by Nazi Germany and the Soviet Union further destabilized the region. The shifting alliances and occupations created a power vacuum and exacerbated existing ethnic and political conflicts. The Nazi occupation of the region and their policies of exploiting ethnic tensions to further their own goals had a significant impact on the dynamics in Volhynia. The Nazis exploited existing divisions and supported nationalist movements, including the Ukrainian Insurgent Army (UPA), to further their own interests. These historical circumstances, characterized by interethnic tensions, territorial disputes, and the impact of World War II, created a volatile environment in which the Volhynia Massacre unfolded.

The following could be considered as specific triggers: the massacres of Ukrainian civilians in response to partisan activity orchestrated in 1942 by the Germans - the UPA blamed Poles for some of

these massacres, fueling their desire for revenge; and the competition for resources: shortages of food and other necessities during the war exacerbated tensions between groups and contributed to violence over access to resources. It's important to note that the historical narratives surrounding these events are disputed. Ukrainian and Polish perspectives can differ on the severity of pre-war tensions, the extent of Polish collaboration with the Nazis, and the motivations behind the UPA's actions.

Diving deeper into its medieval history, we find that Volhynia, located in Eastern Europe, was historically inhabited by East Slavic tribes and became part of the Kievan Rus' federation in the 10th century. It was later incorporated into the Grand Duchy of Lithuania and then the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, experiencing cultural and religious influences from both the Orthodox Christian and Catholic traditions. In the late 18th century, the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth was partitioned by the Russian Empire, the Kingdom of Prussia, and the Habsburg Monarchy. Volhynia came under Russian control, while other parts of the region were absorbed by Austria and Prussia. Under Russian rule, Volhynia experienced russification policies aimed at promoting the Russian language and Orthodox Christianity. This period saw the suppression of Ukrainian cultural and religious practices, contributing to tensions between the Ukrainian and Polish communities. Throughout the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth's existence (1569-1795), Polish culture and language became increasingly dominant, leading to resentment from some Ukrainians in the region. The Khmelnytsky Uprising (1648-1657), rebellion led by Ukrainian Cossack leader Bohdan Khmelnytsky, aimed for autonomy from Polish rule and sparked religious and social conflicts. In the late 18th century, the weakening Commonwealth was partitioned by neighboring empires, with Volhynia falling under Russian control, and the Tsarist regime imposed russification policies aimed at assimilating non-Russian populations, including Ukrainians in Volhynia. Despite these efforts, Ukrainian national identity continued to develop, leading to cultural and political aspirations for autonomy. The collapse of the Russian Empire in 1917 created a power vacuum, leading to a brief period of Ukrainian independence and then a Polish-Ukrainian conflict over the contested territory. The region became part of Poland under the Treaty of Riga (1921), with tensions remaining between Poles and Ukrainians due to perceived political and social inequalities.

Documented inceptions of violence in the region before WW2?

Some of the key instances of violence before World War II include the Polish-Ukrainian Conflict; intermittent clashes between different ethnic and religious groups in the region, including Poles, Ukrainians, and Jews throughout the late 19th and early 20th centuries; pogroms that targeted Jewish

communities and resulted in loss of life, destruction of property, and widespread fear and displacement; as well as disputes over land ownership and access to resources, which at times led to violent confrontations between different ethnic and social groups.

These instances of violence reflected the deep-seated ethnic, religious, and political tensions in the region, which were exacerbated by historical grievances, economic competition, and the shifting power dynamics of the time. The legacy of these conflicts and acts of violence contributed to the underlying tensions that ultimately erupted into the large-scale violence of the Volhynia Massacre during World War II.

Media coverage of the Volhynia massacre

The media coverage of the Volhynia Massacre during and immediately after World War II was limited and often influenced by political agendas and censorship. Due to the chaotic and complex nature of World War II, the international media's coverage of specific events, such as the Volhynia Massacre, was often overshadowed by broader war-related developments. As a result, the massacre received relatively limited attention outside the immediate region. Both the Polish and Soviet governments engaged in propaganda efforts to shape the narrative surrounding the Volhynia Massacre. This included efforts to portray the opposing side as the aggressor and to downplay or distort the scale of the violence.

Despite official censorship and propaganda, there were instances of local and underground reporting on the atrocities in Volhynia. These accounts, often disseminated through clandestine channels and underground publications, provided first hand testimonies of the violence and its impact on local communities. After the war, efforts were made to document and commemorate the events of the Volhynia Massacre. Survivors, historians, and researchers sought to gather testimonies, archival materials, and other evidence to create a more comprehensive record of the violence and its consequences. In recent years, there has been increased scholarly and public interest in the Volhynia Massacre, leading to more extensive historical research and public discourse on the subject. This has resulted in a broader and more nuanced understanding of the events, as well as efforts to acknowledge and commemorate the victims on all sides.

Media coverage still reflects differing perspectives based on national narratives and political viewpoints. Ukrainian and Polish media often present contrasting interpretations, emphasizing their respective victim groups and historical experiences.

Memorial and remembrance

The Volhynia Massacre is a deeply significant and sensitive historical event, and efforts to commemorate it have gained prominence in recent years. In various locations in Poland and Ukraine, there are memorials and commemorative sites dedicated to the victims of the Volhynia Massacre. These include monuments, plaques, and memorial gardens that serve as places of remembrance and reflection. Both Poland and Ukraine have held official commemorations and ceremonies to acknowledge the victims of the Volhynia Massacre. These events often involve government officials, religious leaders, and members of the affected communities coming together to pay tribute to the victims and to reaffirm a commitment to peace and reconciliation. In Poland, there is the Monument to the Martyred Villagers of Volhynia and Eastern Galicia in Warsaw: This central memorial commemorates Polish victims with symbolic sculptures and an eternal flame. In Ukraine, the Memorial Complex "Huta Pieniacka" near the site of a 1943 massacre includes sculptures, exhibits, and an eternal flame.

Scholars, historians, and educators have undertaken efforts to research and document the events of the Volhynia Massacre. This includes the collection of testimonies, archival materials, and the dissemination of historical knowledge to promote a deeper understanding of the complexities and consequences of the massacre. Civil society organizations, cultural institutions, and advocacy groups have worked to raise public awareness about the Volhynia Massacre and facilitate open dialogue about its historical significance. This includes public lectures, exhibitions, and other educational initiatives aimed at fostering greater understanding and empathy.

Reconciliation and apology

The reconciliation between the opposing sides involved in the Volhynia Massacre, particularly the Polish and Ukrainian communities, is an ongoing process. In recent years, there have been some significant steps taken towards reconciliation between Poland and Ukraine, including official public statements and expressions of regret from both Polish and Ukrainian officials regarding the events of the Volhynia Massacre. These acknowledgments have signaled a willingness to address the historical wounds and seek reconciliation. There are also civil society based cross-border initiatives and joint commemorative events and ceremonies to honor the memory of the victims. Both Poland and Ukraine have engaged in some official gestures recognizing the tragedy. Poland established a national day of remembrance, and Ukraine initiated a "Day of Reconciliation" in 2017, though it was less officially recognized. Both are held on July 11th.

Officially, no explicit apologies have been issued regarding the Volhynia massacre. Certain activities and statements could be interpreted as expressing regret or acknowledging the tragedy, such as the adoption of a resolution recognizing the events in Volhynia as a "tragic page" in history and expressing condolences to the families of victims in 2016. Also, almost 80 years after the genocide in Volhynia, President Volodymyr Zelenskyy mentioned the tragedy in 2023, saying "we honor the memory of all innocent victims," without specifying responsibility¹⁸.

Srebrenica

The Srebrenica massacre, which occurred in July 1995 during the Bosnian War, is one of the most tragic events in recent European history. Srebrenica, a town in eastern Bosnia and Herzegovina, was designated as a United Nations Safe Area and was under the protection of Dutch peacekeeping forces at the time. However, in a devastating turn of events, Bosnian Serb forces, led by General Ratko Mladić, overran the enclave, resulting in the mass murder of an estimated 8,000 Bosniak (Bosnian Muslim) men and boys. The victims were systematically separated from the women and children and then executed. Many were buried in mass graves, while others were disposed of in other ways. The brutality and scale of the killings shocked the world and led to widespread condemnation.

The Srebrenica massacre has been recognized as an act of genocide by international courts, including the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia and the International Court of Justice. The tragedy of Srebrenica underscored the failure of the international community to protect civilians and highlighted the urgent need for justice and accountability in the aftermath of the Bosnian War.

Historical circumstances prior to the Srebrenica massacre

The Srebrenica massacre occurred within the broader context of the Bosnian War, a devastating conflict that took place in the 1990s following the breakup of Yugoslavia. The disintegration of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia in the early 1990s led to the emergence of several independent states, including Bosnia and Herzegovina, a country characterized by a diverse population comprising Bosniaks, Bosnian Croats, and Bosnian Serbs, alongside other ethnic and religious groups. In 1992, Bosnia and Herzegovina declared independence from Yugoslavia, prompting a violent and protracted

¹⁸ Syme, P. (2023). Zelenskyy honors victims of World War II massacres of tens of thousands of Poles carried out by Ukrainian nationalists. *Insider Inc.*

conflict. Bosnian Serbs, supported by the Yugoslav People's Army, sought to carve out territories and create a Serb-dominated state, leading to widespread ethnic cleansing and atrocities. Srebrenica was designated as a United Nations Safe Area, intended to provide protection for civilians in the midst of the conflict. However, the effectiveness of the UN protection and peacekeeping missions came under severe strain as Bosnian Serb forces advanced on the enclave. Srebrenica, along with other enclaves such as Sarajevo, faced prolonged sieges and severe humanitarian crises, including shortages of food, medicine, and other essential supplies. The civilian population endured immense suffering and hardship as a result of the conflict. The Srebrenica massacre occurred against the backdrop of the international community's failure to prevent the atrocity. Despite being a designated safe area, Srebrenica was overrun by Bosnian Serb forces, and the Dutch peacekeeping forces were unable to prevent the subsequent mass killings.

The region of Bosnia and Herzegovina has a rich history that spans thousands of years, shaped by diverse cultures, religions, and political influences. In ancient times, the territory of present-day Bosnia and Herzegovina was inhabited by various Illyrian, Celtic, and Roman communities.. The Roman Empire exerted influence over the region, leaving behind architectural and cultural legacies. In the medieval period, Bosnia emerged as an independent kingdom with a unique blend of Christian and Islamic influences. In the 15th century, Bosnia fell under the control of the Ottoman Empire, marking the beginning of over 400 years of Ottoman rule. During this period, the region experienced significant cultural, architectural, and religious transformations, with Islam becoming a dominant faith while preserving the presence of Christian communities. In the late 19th century, Bosnia and Herzegovina came under the administration of the Austro-Hungarian Empire. This period witnessed the modernization of the region, including the development of infrastructure, industry and the introduction of new administrative structures. Following the dissolution of the Austro-Hungarian Empire after World War I, Bosnia and Herzegovina became part of the Kingdom of Serbs, Croats, and Slovenes, which later transformed into the Kingdom of Yugoslavia. During World War II, Bosnia and Herzegovina experienced occupation by Axis powers, and after the war, the region became part of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia under the leadership of Josip Broz Tito, with a socialist government and a multi-ethnic society.

Documented inceptions of violence in the region before the Srebrenica massacre

The Bosnian War, which lasted from 1992 to 1995, was a brutal conflict marked by widespread violence against civilians, including ethnic cleansing, mass killings, and other atrocities. Srebrenica itself had experienced violence throughout the war, including shelling, sniper attacks, and the 1993 Kravica

bus massacre. The war was marked by a series of violent events, including the siege of Sarajevo, the ethnic cleansing campaigns, and the establishment of detention camps where prisoners were subjected to torture and abuse. These events were well-documented by international organizations, journalists, and human rights groups. The escalating violence and human rights abuses in the region were a cause for concern and drew international attention.

Srebrenica massacre in the media

The media coverage of the Srebrenica massacre was extensive and played a significant role in shaping public understanding and the international response to the atrocity. The media covered the Srebrenica massacre with a mix of on-the-ground reporting, interviews with survivors and witnesses, and analysis of the political and military context. The coverage highlighted the scale of the atrocity, the systematic nature of the killings, and the failure of the international community to prevent or intervene to stop the massacre. Journalists and news organizations documented the horrific details of the massacre, including mass executions, forced deportations, and the desperate plight of the survivors. The media coverage brought the human tragedy of Srebrenica to the forefront of global attention, prompting widespread outrage and calls for justice. However, it has also raised questions about the role of the international community, particularly the United Nations and its peacekeeping forces, in failing to protect the designated "safe area" of Srebrenica. The media's scrutiny of the international response and the failure to prevent the massacre contributed to a reevaluation of policies and actions in conflict zones.

However, the initial reports were often fragmentary and lacked concrete details due to limited access and conflicting narratives from different parties. Media attention initially focused on the safety of Dutch UN troops stationed in Srebrenica, portraying them as victims rather than highlighting the plight of civilians. Serbian authorities initially denied responsibility for the massacre, sowing confusion and delaying international action.

Memorial and remembrance

The official commemoration typically takes place on July 11th, marking the anniversary of the massacre's peak in 1995. On that day, various events are held, including ceremonies at the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial and Cemetery, speeches by dignitaries, and educational initiatives aimed

at remembering the victims and raising awareness about the tragedy. Continuous media coverage and discussions: Articles, documentaries, and discussions keep the event in the public eye, promoting reflection and critical engagement.

Some Serbian leaders have formally apologized for the massacre, including President Boris Tadic in 2010¹⁹ and President Tomislav Nikolić in 2013²⁰. However, these apologies have been criticized for being insufficient, often failing to acknowledge the full extent of the crime or its designation as genocide. Leaders of the Bosnian Serb entity, Republika Srpska, have been more reluctant to acknowledge responsibility or offer apologies. Some, like Republika Srpska's President Milorad Dodik, have even made statements downplaying the massacre or denying its genocidal nature. In 2007, the Serbian state expressed "deepest remorse" for the "tragic events" in Srebrenica, and in 2010, the Serbian parliament adopted a declaration "condemning in strongest terms the crime committed in July 1995 against the Bosniak population of Srebrenica" and offered condolences to the families of the victims. As mentioned, President Tomislav Nikolić apologized, stating, "I kneel and ask for forgiveness for Serbia for the crime committed in Srebrenica." However, these statements have been criticized as insufficient because none of them explicitly label the events in Srebrenica as "genocide," as recognized by the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia and the International Court of Justice.

An attempt to compare evil deeds: Jasenovac, Volhynia, and Srebrenica

So, is there a pattern to committing genocide?

There are some patterns and commonalities in the commission of genocide. While each genocide is unique in its historical and political context, there are recurring patterns and factors that contribute to the commission of such atrocities. Some of the common patterns and contributing factors include: dehumanization, ethnic or religious tensions, state-sponsored or organized violence, propaganda and hate speech, and international indifference or complicity.

Genocide often involves the dehumanization of the targeted group, where they are portrayed as less than human or as a threat to the perpetrators' identity or existence. This dehumanization can make it

¹⁹ Stojanovic, D. (2010). Serbian Parliament apologizes for 1995 Srebrenica, Bosnia, massacre; President Boris Tadic says it strengthens links to EU. *Associated Press*.

²⁰ Ristic, M. (2013). Serbian President Apologises for War Crimes. *BIRN*.

easier for perpetrators to justify and carry out mass violence against the targeted group. “Dehumanization is a common precursor to genocide, as it involves portraying the targeted group as subhuman, dangerous, or unworthy of empathy. This can be achieved through propaganda, hate speech, and the use of derogatory language to create a narrative that justifies violence against the targeted group.”²¹

Also, genocides frequently occur in the context of longstanding ethnic or religious tensions, where historical grievances and animosities are manipulated and exploited by political or military leaders to mobilize support for violence against a particular group. “Genocides often occur within the context of historical ethnic or religious tensions, where competition over land, resources, or political power exacerbates existing divisions and grievances. Political leaders may exploit these tensions to mobilize support for violence against a particular group.”²²

Another common distinction is that genocides often involve the systematic and organized use of state institutions, military forces, or paramilitary groups, as Kiernan (2007) remarks: “Genocides often involve the systematic and organized use of state institutions, military forces, or paramilitary groups to carry out mass killings and other forms of violence against the targeted group. This can include the establishment of concentration camps, mass executions, and forced displacement.”²³

Dissemination of propaganda and hate speech often precedes genocides in order to demonize and vilify the targeted group, creating a climate of fear and hatred that justifies and incites violence. “The use of propaganda and hate speech plays a significant role in creating a climate of fear and hatred that justifies and incites violence against the targeted group. This can involve the dissemination of false or dehumanizing narratives through the media, speeches, and public statements.”²⁴

International indifference or complicity is another similarity - “Genocides can be facilitated by the indifference or inaction of the international community, as well as by the active support or complicity of external actors, including neighboring states or global powers. This can involve factors such as geopolitical interests, diplomatic calculations, or the failure to intervene to prevent mass atrocities.”²⁵

²¹ Power, S. (2003). *A Problem from Hell: America and the Age of Genocide*. Harper Perennial.

²² Chalk, F., Jonassohn, K. (1990). *The History and Sociology of Genocide: Analyses and Case Studies*. Yale University Press.

²³ Kiernan, B. (2007). *Blood and Soil: A World History of Genocide and Extermination from Sparta to Darfur*. Yale University Press.

²⁴ Kuper, L. (1985). *The Prevention of Genocide*. Yale University Press.

²⁵ Power, S. (2001). *Bystanders to Genocide*. The Atlantic.

These are just a few of the recurring patterns and contributing factors in the commission of genocide. The events of Srebrenica, Volhynia, and Jasenovac exemplify some of these patterns, as demonstrated in the historical references provided.

It must be noted that using the given parameters as described above, the three genocides happened at different times in different contexts and circumstances. Yet, there are striking similarities to be spotted even with the naked eye.

However, attempting to be empirical, let's start with the differences first. There is obviously a difference between perpetrators and victims: In Jasenovac the Ustasha regime perpetrated atrocities against Serbs, Jews, Roma, and others; in Volhynia, the Ukrainian Insurgent Army targeted primarily the Polish population; and in Srebrenica, Serb forces massacred Bosniak Muslim civilians.

Also, there is a difference regarding the context and motivations: Jasenovac operated as a concentration camp during World War II, driven by the Ustasha regime's genocidal ideology and Nazi collaboration; Volhynia was part of a broader cycle of violence during World War II, fueled by historical grievances, competition for land, and wartime chaos; and the massacre in Srebrenica occurred during the Bosnian War, motivated by ethnic cleansing and territorial ambitions.

A third set of differences could be regarded in the context of the international response to the atrocities: Jasenovac is recognized as a concentration and extermination camp by the UN and other international bodies, while the recognition of the Volhynia massacre as a crime against humanity varies, with ongoing debates about specific classifications. The massacre in Srebrenica is considered a genocide by the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia.

The similarities between the three events can also be divided into three sets, although there is more to be discussed. Firstly, all three genocides were carried out during periods of intense ethnic or religious conflict. The Jasenovac genocide occurred during the Holocaust, as part of the Ustasha regime's campaign against Serbs, Jews, and Roma people in Croatia. The Volhynia massacre took place during World War II, in the context of the conflict between Poles and Ukrainians. The Srebrenica genocide occurred during the Bosnian War, which was characterized by ethnic tensions between Bosnian Muslims and Bosnian Serbs.

Secondly, all three genocides involved the deliberate targeting of a specific ethnic or religious group. In Jasenovac, the Ustasha regime targeted Serbs, Jews, and Roma people for extermination. In Volhynia, Ukrainian nationalists targeted Polish civilians, particularly women and children. In Srebrenica, Bosnian Serb forces specifically targeted Bosnian Muslim men and boys for execution. In this manner, we can

conclude that in at least two of the analyzed genocides, there were documented cases that included targets of not only one group but of all that were opposing the regime (Roma and Jews in Jasenovac, Belarus in Volhynia).

Additionally, all three genocides involved large-scale violence and mass killings of civilians. In Srebrenica, an estimated 8,000 people were killed in the span of a few days. In Volhynia, tens of thousands of civilians were killed, and in Jasenovac, hundreds of thousands of people were killed in the concentration camp.

Overall, while the specific historical and political contexts of these genocides differ, there are clear similarities in terms of the deliberate targeting of specific ethnic or religious groups and the large-scale violence and mass killings of civilian populations that occurred.

To break down, we can note that common features are the civilian targeting - all three involved the deliberate killing of civilians, including women, children, and the elderly; the ethnic/religious motivations - each massacre was driven, at least in part, by ethnic and/or religious hatred and animosity; the scale and brutality - all inflicted significant loss of life and employed brutal methods of killing; as well as the lasting impact - all three left deep scars on the collective memory of the affected communities and continue to shape relations between groups.

Another common feature, which could be a theme of analysis for a separate piece of paper itself, is the denial of the genocides by one of the parties (states or nations). This means that the genocides are rarely mentioned or not at all mentioned in the historiography of the party, which is in any manner connected to the perpetrators (Volhynia in Ukraine, Jasenovac in Croatia, and Srebrenica in Serbia).

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Unless otherwise indicated, all data and descriptions of historical or geographical facts and figures in this paper stem from the cross-reference of information obtained from the following resources:

Encyclopaedia Britannica (www.britannica.com),

Facing History & Ourselves (www.facinghistory.org),

The United Nations (www.un.org),

Yad Vashem - The World Holocaust Remembrance Center (www.yadvashem.org),

United States Holocaust Memorial Museum (www.ushmm.org), and

Cambridge University (www.cambridge.org).